

1 **Identification of cell and tumor type-specific Xist RNA/protein complexes: BAZ2A.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 We recently described (1) a mechanism of transcriptional regulation, in human cancer and in
7 development, wherein the non-coding RNA responsible for X-inactivation, Xist, is modulated in the
8 presence of p53 mutation, or induced following loss of p53 tumor suppression, representing a novel and
9 biologically relevant method of transcriptional regulation in solid tumors.

10 To understand the precise mechanism by which Xist exerts ectopic function in human cancer, we studied
11 whole transcription in human cells genetically engineered to contain an Xist transgene (10) to identify Xist
12 interactants, as well as human embryonic stem cells which were positive for Xist expression at the clonal
13 level or were derived from a male or female and thus Xist-positive or Xist- negative at the population level.

14 We provide evidence here demonstrating the presence of bromodomain adjacent to zinc finger domain
15 2A, encoded by *BAZ2A* in a cell- or tumor -type specific RNP complex containing Xist. Importantly, we
16 found evidence indicating *BAZ2A* and a second gene, *BAZ2B*, were core members of an Xist RNP
17 complex and were present in the Xist RNP mutually exclusive states.

Methods

We studied differential gene expression in p53 wild-type and p53 deficient breast cancer cells, where Xist modulation by p53 was discovered, in human cells transgenically expressing Xist, and in embryonic stem cells from mice genetically engineered to lack p53 expression using the R-based application GEO2R. GSE57083 was generated using Affymetrix Human Genome U133 Plus 2.0 Array microarray technology with $n=2$ breast cancer cell lines with wild-type p53 (MCF7 and ZR751) and $n=2$ breast cancer cell lines with mutant p53 (T47D and BT549); platform GPL570 was utilized. GSE26362 was generated using Affymetrix Mouse Gene 1.0 ST Array [transcript (gene) version] microarray technology with $n=2$ wild-type embryonic stem cells (R1E) and $n=2$ p53 $-/-$ embryonic stem cells (129X1 x 129S1); platform GPL6246 was utilized. GSE68109 was generated using Illumina HiSeq 2500 (Homo sapiens) RNA-sequencing technology with $n=1$ HT1080 fibrosarcoma cell line with 8p Xist integration (day 1; no doxycycline) and $n=2$ HT-1080 fibrosarcoma cell line with Xist integration (day 5; doxycycline induction); platform GPL16791 was utilized. We used SEEK for computational co-regulation study (13).

Results

We previously utilized published mass spectrometric data to deconvolute the composition of this hypothetical complex, revealing the RNA-binding protein KHDRBS1 was a *bona fide* protein interaction partner of Xist (2). We continued here discovery and description of an Xist RNP complex using p53 wild-type and deficient cancer cells, cells genetically engineered to express Xist, p53 deficient mouse embryonic stem cells where Xist is induced, and using a systems biological methodology which probes whole transcription across multiple settings to discover transcriptionally co-regulated genes.

Figure 1: BAZ2A is transcriptionally activated in Xist+ human embryonic stem cells.

GSE87321

$n=2$ Xist-negative human embryonic stem cell clones

$n=2$ Xist-positive human embryonic stem cell clones

ID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	% DE
7503	4.04e-43	0.24	-13.7668188	-3.30500185	2704.58	XIST	5/17710	99.97*
11176	6.51E-03	0.132	-2.7207958	-0.35891105	4811.02	BAZ2A	1850/17710	89.6
29994	2.80E-01	0.585	1.0810236	0.63272346	390.97	BAZ2B	7496/17710	57.7

BAZ2B was modestly silenced in Xist+ hES concomitant with BAZ2A induction. We next examined p53 deficient breast cancer cell lines where we originally discovered Xist modulation in cancer cells with a p53-deficient genetic background (Figure 2).

Figure 2: BAZ2A is modestly transcriptionally activated in p53 deficient cancer cells concomitant with Xist modulation.

GSE57083

$n=2$ breast cancer cell lines with wild-type p53 (MCF7 and ZR751)

$n=2$ breast cancer cell lines with mutant p53 (T47D and BT549)

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	% DE
224589_at	0.0000218	2.87E+01	-4.25	5.14489344	XIST	2/54675	99.996
215437_x_at	0.283606	-1.26	-4.56	-0.26690973	BAZ2A	16568/54675	69.7
203080_s_at	0.0155553	4.32	-4.32	1.18618626	BAZ2B	754/54675	98.6

In addition to modest BAZ2A induction, BAZ2B was silenced concomitant with Xist repression resulting from p53 loss in vitro.

To validate a role for BAZ2A as a component of the Xist RNP complex, which we hypothesize to exist in many variant forms which will be a function of the quantity of available complex members present, we examined whole transcription in human cells genetically engineered to express Xist (Chart 3).

Figure 3: Transgenic expression of Xist in human cells results in transcriptional induction of BAZ2A.

GSE68109

n=1 HT1080 fibrosarcoma cell line with 8p Xist integration (day 1; no doxycycline [DOX])

n=2 HT1080 fibrosarcoma cell line with 8p Xist integration (5 day DOX induction)

ID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	% DE
7503	0	0.0949	-5.07E+01	-4.81	42145.57	XIST	1/18377	99.99
11176	3.67E-06	0.0972	-4.63	-4.50E-01	9410.86	BAZ2A	972/18377	94.7

Expression of Xist resulted in transcriptional induction of BAZ2A in human cells transgenically engineered to express Xist (Figure 3). The data demonstrated that expression of Xist in human cells was sufficient to result in differential expression of BAZ2A.

We next evaluated whole transcription in mouse embryonic stem cells with engineered deletion of p53, in which we have previously demonstrated Xist induction (1).

Figure 4: BAZ2A is differentially expressed in sex-specific human embryonic stem cells endogenously expressing Xist, but repressed rather than activated.

GSE102311

n=2 hES cells (XY [male])

n=2 hES cells (XX [female])

ID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
7503	3.47E-256	0.2293	-34.189422	-7.8381775	2417.91	XIST	5/19799	99.97
11176	1.52E-06	0.0377	4.808785	0.1814045	5891.5	BAZ2A	1060/19799	94.6

Figure 5: Deletion of p53 in mouse embryonic stem cells, which results in modest Xist induction, results in silencing of BAZ2A.

GSE26362

n=2 wild-type embryonic stem cells (R1E)

n=2 p53 -/- embryonic stem cells (129X1 x 129S1)

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	% DE
10606178	2.44e-07	-13.3827038	7.26104	-1.24452642	Xist	2894/ 28815	90.0 (1)
10474006	1.04E-05	8.6390903	3.194392	1.48606725	BAZ2A	6268/28815	78.2

Changes in BAZ2A transcription we measured blindly using whole transcriptome technologies continued to demonstrate control of BAZ2A expression by Xist, indicating a BAZ2A Xist interaction. BAZ2A was repressed upon p53 deletion and Xist induction, suggesting species- or p53 mutation status-specific differences in Xist RNP complex composition.

After establishing that expression of BAZ2A was controlled by Xist in human cells expressing Xist, we examined transcriptional co-regulation by BAZ2A to understand if BAZ2A was co-regulated with genes to which have previously described as belonging to the Xist RNP, including KHDRBS1, ILF2 and ILF3.

We interrogated a computational co-regulation tool known as SEEK (12), which queries whole transcriptome expression patterns across a variety of cellular contexts, identifying in an unbiased fashion the Xist RNP components KHDRBS1 and ILF3 (Figure 1).

Figure 5: BAZ2A is co-regulated with KDM5C, an Xist co-regulated gene product.

Query genes:

Rank	Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	p-value	Rank	%Co-reg
	BAZ2A	51317	-3.2	0.0025		

Coexpressed genes:

Rank	Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	p-value	Rank	%Co-reg
	KHDRBS1	10657	1.69	0.0112	61/17862	99.7
	ILF3	3609	1.815	0.0238	27/17862	99.8

Xist interacts with known localization factors, including SPEN, CIZ, and ATRX. We studied transcriptional co-regulation by BAZ2A to understand whether BAZ2A was co-regulated with any known Xist interacting proteins (Chart 4). We found BAZ2A was closely co-regulated with SPEN, CIZ and ATRX. Thus, BAZ2A existed in a transcriptional co-regulated network with known Xist-interacting proteins as well as genes we described as belonging to a novel Xist RNP complex (Chart 4 and Figure 1).

Figure 6: SPEN, CIZ, and ATRX, Xist-interacting proteins, are BAZ2A co-regulated genes.

Query genes:

Rank	Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	p-value	Rank	%Co-reg
	BAZ2A	51317	-3.2	0.0025		

Coexpressed genes:

Rank	Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	p-value	Rank	%Co-reg
	SPEN	23013	1.335	0.0312	329/17862	98.2
	ATRX	546	1.615	0.0208	93/17862	99.5
	CIZ1	25792	1.4258	0.0272	209/17862	98.8

Figure 7: BAZ2A is a CIZ1 (ZNF384) co-regulated gene.

Query genes:

Rank	Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	p-value	Rank	%Co-reg
	CIZ1	25792	-3.2000	0.0022	CDKN1A	

Coexpressed genes:

Rank	Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	p-value	Rank	%Co-reg
	BAZ2A	11176	1.1933	0.0411	496/17858	97.2

Discussion

p53 controls Xist expression in transformed settings as a direct consequence of tumor suppressor inactivation. We demonstrated here that Xist controls expression of an Xist-binding partner, BAZ2A, in human embryonic stem cells and that this is independent of p53 status. The composition of the Xist RNP complex will likely vary by cell type, species, and p53 status which often but not always governs transformation. This complex we predict functions to drive tumor progression by enhancing fitness of tumor clones through genomic instability driven primarily epigenetically. We provided here evidence indicating the presence of BAZ2A in an Xist-containing RNP complex.

References

1. Mamoor, S., 2023. The tumor suppressor p53 regulates Xist expression in certain cellular contexts.
2. Mamoor, S., 2024. Identification of cell and tumor type-specific Xist RNA/protein complexes.
3. Li, M., He, Y., Dubois, W., Wu, X., Shi, J. and Huang, J., 2012. Distinct regulatory mechanisms and functions for p53-activated and p53-repressed DNA damage response genes in embryonic stem cells. *Molecular cell*, 46(1), pp.30-42.
4. GSE57083. Astra Zeneca Cell Line Database. Oncology, Bioinformatics. Macclesfield, UK.
5. Chu, C., Zhang, Q.C., Da Rocha, S.T., Flynn, R.A., Bharadwaj, M., Calabrese, J.M., Magnuson, T., Heard, E. and Chang, H.Y., 2015. Systematic discovery of Xist RNA binding proteins. *Cell*, 161(2), pp.404-416.
6. Sunwoo, H., Colognori, D., Froberg, J.E., Jeon, Y. and Lee, J.T., 2017. Repeat E anchors Xist RNA to the inactive X chromosomal compartment through CDKN1A-interacting protein (CIZ1). *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 114(40), pp.10654-10659.
7. Minajigi, A., Froberg, J.E., Wei, C., Sunwoo, H., Kesner, B., Colognori, D., Lessing, D., Payer, B., Boukhali, M., Haas, W. and Lee, J.T., 2015. A comprehensive Xist interactome reveals cohesin repulsion and an RNA-directed chromosome conformation. *Science*, 349(6245), p.aab2276.
8. Pandya-Jones, A., Markaki, Y., Serizay, J., Chitashvili, T., Mancina Leon, W.R., Damianov, A., Chronis, C., Papp, B., Chen, C.K., McKee, R. and Wang, X.J., 2020. A protein assembly mediates Xist localization and gene silencing. *Nature*, 587(7832), pp.145-151.
9. Aguilar, R., Spencer, K.B., Kesner, B., Rizvi, N.F., Badmalia, M.D., Mrozowich, T., Mortison, J.D., Rivera, C., Smith, G.F., Burchard, J. and Dandliker, P.J., 2022. Targeting Xist with compounds that disrupt RNA structure and X inactivation. *Nature*, 604(7904), pp.160-166.
10. Sarma, K., Cifuentes-Rojas, C., Ergun, A., Del Rosario, A., Jeon, Y., White, F., Sadreyev, R. and Lee, J.T., 2014. ATRX directs binding of PRC2 to Xist RNA and Polycomb targets. *Cell*, 159(4), pp.869-883.
11. Li, M., He, Y., Dubois, W., Wu, X., Shi, J. and Huang, J., 2012. Distinct regulatory mechanisms and functions for p53-activated and p53-repressed DNA damage response genes in embryonic stem cells. *Molecular cell*, 46(1), pp.30-42.
12. Kelsey, A.D., Yang, C., Leung, D., Minks, J., Dixon-McDougall, T., Baldry, S.E., Bogutz, A.B., Lefebvre, L. and Brown, C.J., 2015. Impact of flanking chromosomal sequences on localization and silencing by the human non-coding RNA XIST. *Genome biology*, 16, pp.1-16.
13. Zhu, Q., Wong, A.K., Krishnan, A., Aure, M.R., Tadych, A., Zhang, R., Corney, D.C., Greene, C.S., Bongo, L.A., Kristensen, V.N. and Charikar, M., 2015. Targeted exploration and analysis of large cross-platform human transcriptomic compendia. *Nature methods*, 12(3), pp.211-214.